

Espacenet

Bibliographic data: EP3792341 (A1) — 2021-03-17

METHOD FOR GENERATING A TISSUE

Inventor(s): BAENA MARTÍNEZ JOSÉ MANUEL [ES] ± (BAENA MARTÍNEZ, José Manuel)

Applicant(s): REGEMAT 3D S L [ES] ± (Regemat 3D S.L)

Classification: - international: **A61F2/28; A61F2/30; C12M1/12; C12M1/26; C12M1/42; C12M3/00**
 - cooperative: **A61F2/2846 (EP); A61F2/30756 (EP); C12M21/08 (EP); C12M25/14 (EP); C12M33/00 (EP); C12M35/04 (EP); A61F2002/30766 (EP)**

Application number: EP20190382798 20190916 Unitary patent Global Dossier

Priority number(s): EP20190382798 20190916

Also published as: EP3792341 (B1) EP3792341 (C0) ES3004536 (T3)

Abstract of EP3792341 (A1)

The invention provides a method for generating a tissue. This method comprises providing a physical model of a patient's joint (1), replacing a damaged element (2) of the physical model with a scaffold (3), introducing the physical model (1) with the scaffold (3) in a bioreactor (10) and start cell culture around the scaffold (3). Some standard movements are simulated on the physical model (1) while the cell culture is taking place, so that the tissue is generated around the scaffold (3). The invention also refers to a bioreactor (10) to carry out the steps of this method.

Fig. 3